

Sophisticated common support selection for treatment analyses

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Abstract. This paper examines the role of the region of common support (RCS) in causal inference using propensity score-based methods. Although techniques such as propensity score matching and inverse-probability weighting rely critically on overlap between treated and control units, the construction and restriction of the RCS are often treated as secondary implementation details. We show that inadequate handling of the RCS can lead to biased estimates or substantial losses in external validity. To address this issue, we introduce `comsup`, a Stata command that provides a flexible framework for estimating treatment models, assessing overlap, and restricting the RCS using trimming and pruning procedures. The command integrates lasso-based model selection for propensity score estimation and allows users to incorporate outcome information for more parsimonious specifications. Using Monte Carlo simulations, we demonstrate that proper RCS handling can meaningfully improve estimator performance, but that the benefits depend on the degree of treatment effect heterogeneity. In particular, strict RCS restrictions may worsen performance when heterogeneous treatment effects are strong, highlighting an important trade-off in applied work.

Keywords: region of common support, propensity score methods, treatment effect heterogeneity, causal inference, Stata

1 Introduction

Whenever the goal is to estimate (causal) treatment effects, one of the most important requirements is a “fair,” that is, valid comparison between the treatment and control groups. Statisticians refer to this as internal validity, meaning that apples are not compared with oranges. Achieving such validity is often challenging when treatment assignment has not been randomized in an experimental setting and only observational

data are available. Although it has long been established theoretically that methods based on statistical adjustment can yield unbiased estimates of treatment effects, achieving this in practice may remain difficult, even when all relevant confounders have been identified and measured adequately.

Many widely used statistical methods, such as propensity score matching, nearest-neighbor matching, and inverse-probability weighting, rely on the propensity score and the region of common support to estimate treatment effects. Although there are many ways to estimate the propensity score (the probability that a given observation receives treatment) there are also multiple approaches for defining the region of common support, that is, the overlap in treatment probabilities between treatment and control groups. In other words, the propensity score is derived from the treatment model, a statistical model that researchers must specify carefully to obtain reliable results. Conversely, observations outside the region of common support are analogous to oranges in a pool of apples: no valid comparison group can be identified for them because their background characteristics differ so substantially from those of other observations that they remain “incomparable.” Excluding such observations may improve treatment effect estimation, but it also carries the risk of producing a selective sample that is no longer representative of the population of interest.

In this paper, we discuss several pitfalls related to specifying a well-designed treatment model and carefully selecting the region of common support, issues relevant for a broad range of statistical methods. We introduce the Stata command `comsup`, which allows users to manage this process conveniently. Finally, we present results from a simulation study demonstrating how this command can improve treatment effect estimation, while also illustrating circumstances under which undesirable results may arise.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 General approach

In social and medical science research, randomly assigning the treatment of interest is often impossible for ethical or practical reasons. The absence of a randomized counterfactual poses a fundamental challenge for studies aimed at estimating causal effects because it introduces the possibility of selection bias due to confounding variables. To address this issue, various methods have been developed, including propensity score matching (PSM) and inverse-probability weighting (IPW). In this section, we introduce these approaches for approximating causal effects when only observational data are available.

The first step is to select relevant potential confounders as control variables. A confounder is a variable that affects both treatment assignment and the outcome variable (Pearl 2009). In general, this selection should be based on theoretical considerations, because no statistical test can determine whether an effect is “causal.” A causal interpretation is only plausible when all relevant confounders have been identified and adequately measured; otherwise, the association between treatment and outcome may

remain biased and spurious.

Second, both PSM and IPW rely on propensity scores, that is, the probability of treatment assignment computed for treated and untreated observations conditional on a set of relevant covariates. In practice, the propensity score is unknown and must be estimated through a model, usually logit or probit, where propensity scores are defined as $P(T = 1 | X)$, with X denoting a vector of selected covariates. The main advantage of the propensity score is that it reduces a potentially high-dimensional set of covariates to a one-dimensional balancing score. As shown by Rosenbaum and Rubin (Rosenbaum and Rubin 1983), the propensity score addresses the curse of dimensionality, meaning that balancing all confounders directly across all possible covariate combinations is typically infeasible, even in large datasets.

A major challenge at this stage is specifying an adequate treatment model. Although several model types are available (typically logit or probit, though linear probability models are also possible in principle), correct specification is crucial. Researchers often include only main effects, which may be insufficient. Both covariates and higher-order terms, such as interactions and squared terms, should be considered according to theoretical expectations. The same applies to covariate selection more generally: theory should guide the researcher, but conditioning treatment assignment on confounders is essential. If a variable affects both the outcome and the probability of treatment, it should be included in the model. The inclusion of higher-order covariates may also follow a more empirical procedure. If strata are imbalanced, the treatment model can be respecified by adding higher-order terms. However, it is generally preferable to improve balance first by reducing stratum size. As noted above, treatment model specification should be theoretically informed rather than data driven. Practical guidance on assessing stratum balance and respecifying the treatment model is provided by Li (2013).

Third, the propensity score distributions of treated and untreated units define the region of common support (RCS), that is, the region in which the two distributions overlap and a plausible counterfactual exists. In the following, we discuss in detail how the RCS may be selected. PSM uses the propensity score as the criterion for matching treated observations with the most similar untreated observations within the RCS, using the latter as counterfactuals for estimating treatment effects. One straightforward algorithm is nearest-neighbor (NN) matching, in which control units are matched to the closest treated units. With NN matching with replacement, distance is typically defined as the smallest absolute difference in propensity scores. However, even the closest match may still be too distant to be credible. For this reason, a caliper is often imposed. A caliper defines a tolerance threshold; if a unit can only be matched by exceeding this threshold, it is excluded. These are only examples among many matching algorithms. Others include radius, interval, kernel matching (KM), and local linear matching (LLM) (Caliendo and Kopeinig 2008).

Because a sufficiently close match may not exist for some observations, many units may be excluded from the analysis. Although procedurally appropriate, such exclusion can be particularly burdensome in small datasets. Poor matches often arise in the tails of the RCS, where untreated units with high propensity scores, and vice versa, are rare.

IPW estimators are commonly used to address this issue. IPW assigns each unit a weight equal to the inverse probability of receiving the treatment it actually received ($1/PS$ for treated units and $1/(1 - PS)$ for controls). In this way, rare observations contribute more to the estimates than common ones. By assigning larger weights to rare observations, such as untreated units with high propensity scores, IPW creates a pseudo-population in which treatment assignment is independent of observed covariates.

A note of caution concerns observations with extreme propensity scores, which may receive disproportionately large weights. An alternative is AIPW (augmented inverse-probability weighting), which combines weighting with outcome modeling and can partially mitigate excessive influence from outliers through its doubly robust property. However, AIPW should not be viewed as a remedy for poor overlap, because it cannot resolve fundamental violations of common support. Both PSM and IPW are appropriate only if the strong ignorability assumption holds. First, treatment assignment must be independent of potential outcomes conditional on covariates, implying that after conditioning on relevant covariates, treatment is as-if random. Second, common support must hold, meaning that for all covariate values there is a positive probability of assignment to either treatment or control. The first part of this assumption is not directly testable, whereas the common support condition can be assessed empirically.

When the common support assumption is violated, analysis should not proceed without adjustment. In such cases, it is common to redefine the RCS by excluding part of the sample. Importantly, redefining the RCS is not a neutral procedure: it changes the target population, affects generalizability, and may shift the estimand from the ATE to treatment effects for a subpopulation. Therefore, before redefining the RCS, it is advisable to inspect the propensity score distributions of treated and control groups to assess the extent of the overlap problem. Many approaches exist for redefining the RCS. The simplest trims observations at the minimum and maximum propensity score values, thereby removing the extreme tails of the distribution. This approach targets observations that are unlikely to overlap. However, its simplicity also entails shortcomings. First, if multiple extreme values lack overlap, trimming only the single most extreme value may be insufficient. Second, trimming only at the boundaries ignores possible lack of overlap within the interior of the distribution. While the first issue may be addressed by trimming, for example, the 10 smallest and 10 largest propensity score values, the second requires more sophisticated procedures. One such approach trims all observations below a density threshold, thereby addressing lack of overlap throughout the distribution rather than only at its edges.

Redefining the RCS involves a clear bias–variance trade-off. By eliminating observations, trimming reduces sample size and may increase variance, while potentially reducing bias due to incomparable observations. Intuitively, the “apples with apples” principle narrows the set of observations considered, which may improve internal validity at the cost of external validity. Although some methods (Lechner and Strittmatter 2019; Lechner 2008; Huber et al. 2013) can mitigate this trade-off, it remains an inherent feature of RCS redefinition and should be explicitly acknowledged. One recommended practice is one-sided trimming of treated units whose propensity scores exceed the maximum (or 99% quantile) propensity score in the control group. The rationale is that,

when estimating the ATT, treated units define the population of interest, whereas controls serve instrumentally to construct a plausible counterfactual. Thus, treated units are discarded only when no credible counterfactual exists for them.

2.2 Heterogeneous treatment effects

As discussed above, selecting the region of common support (RCS) is a crucial step in the analysis. If the RCS is not restricted at all and the overlap condition is violated, invalid comparisons arise, leading to biased estimates because apples are compared with oranges. Conversely, if the RCS is restricted too aggressively, the remaining sample may differ substantially from the original sample, creating problems for external validity. Although the resulting comparison may be internally valid and statistically well defined, conclusions may no longer generalize to the initial sample or the target population, potentially undermining the substantive value of the analysis.

The issue becomes even more complicated in the presence of heterogeneous treatment effects. Heterogeneous treatment effects arise when the effect of the treatment varies across observations or subgroups. In such cases, the Average Treatment Effect on the Treated (ATT) and the Average Treatment Effect on the Controls (ATC) may differ substantially.¹ As we demonstrate in a simple simulation below, aggressive restriction of the RCS can be particularly problematic when treatment effects are heterogeneous.

To build intuition for this problem, consider the following. If the causal effect of treatment varies across subgroups defined by confounders, this suggests that the factors determining treatment assignment may themselves depend strongly on those same confounders. When strong treatment effect heterogeneity exists, the selection mechanism can become highly specific. For example, a particular combination of confounders may make treatment especially effective for one subgroup, while also making treatment assignment in that subgroup highly predictable. Such dependencies often manifest as imbalance in the tails of the confounder distribution. If a particular confounding profile makes treatment nearly mandatory, the proportion of control observations in that subgroup may become extremely small.

When the probability of treatment, conditional on the confounding vector, approaches zero or one for a subgroup, that subgroup falls outside the region of common support and is excluded from the analysis, even though it may be substantively important and represent a meaningful share of the population. As a consequence, treatment effects estimated in the remaining sample may differ substantially from those in the full population.

To illustrate this issue, we construct a simple example with a single continuous, approximately normally distributed confounding variable X , a binary treatment variable (with unequal group sizes, where only about 22% of observations receive treatment), and a continuous outcome variable (Figure 1).

1. Note that, whenever this is the case, regression coefficients cannot generally be interpreted as the ATE and may be biased (Słoczyński 2022).

Figure 1: When heterogeneous treatment effects are present, removing observations through common support restrictions can critically alter results because the remaining sample may no longer represent the population of interest.

The upper-left panel shows the relationship between confounder X and the probability of receiving treatment, revealing a strong positive association. The upper-right panel illustrates treatment effect heterogeneity, as the magnitude of the treatment effect depends on the value of X . The lower-left panel shows the propensity score distribution and demonstrates that a sizeable share of observations is removed even when only a single percentile is trimmed from both tails. However, because this relatively small group contributes substantially to the ATE, imposing strict common support restrictions biases the estimated ATE (lower-right panel); the unbiased ATE in this example is 5.

More generally, heterogeneous treatment effects present a major challenge for causal inference. Researchers should be cautious when the ATT differs substantially from the ATC, as this may indicate important heterogeneity. In such settings, methods that rely heavily on strict common support restrictions may be problematic, and alternative approaches may be preferable.

3 The `comsup` command

3.1 Approach

Common support selection for treatment effect analysis should be both convenient and flexible. With `comsup`, we present an easy-to-use Stata command that facilitates the rapid specification of powerful treatment models while providing users substantial control over the process. In a first step, users specify all variables believed to predict treatment assignment, analogous to existing commands such as `teffects`. The only additional requirement is that categorical variables be declared using Stata's `i.` prefix. `comsup` then estimates a lasso model for the treatment variable, including interactions and higher-order terms while retaining only those selected as relevant (Ranstam and Cook 2018). Although estimation can be computationally demanding, this approach aims to identify a powerful yet sparse model while minimizing the risk of overfitting. In principle, users may further modify the lasso specification as desired. By default, the command uses a logit model for treatment assignment, although alternative specifications are available (including linear models, which are considerably faster). Based on the final selected model, the propensity score is then estimated.

Users also have the option to include the outcome variable in model selection. If this option is chosen, two lasso models are estimated, one for treatment assignment and one for the outcome. The command then retains only variables and terms selected as predictors in both models. Based on the estimated propensity score, that is, the predicted probability that each observation receives treatment, users can define the region of common support. In a first and mandatory step, the main region is defined as the overlap between the minimum and maximum propensity score values in the treatment and control groups. This corresponds to the standard common support restriction implemented in other commands, such as `kmatch` with the `comsup` option.

In a second step, users may optionally prune the propensity score distribution. Here, the propensity score is divided into n equally sized brackets (not necessarily containing the same number of observations), and the numbers of treated and control observations are counted within each bracket. If the number of observations in either group falls below a user-specified threshold, all observations in that bracket are discarded. The advantage of this approach is that it can detect and remove “empty” or weakly supported regions within the interior of the propensity score distribution—regions that conventional approaches based solely on extreme values may fail to identify. As a further option, the resulting common support region may be additionally restricted through trimming, which removes the i th specified percentile from both tails of the propensity score distribution. If desired, this trimming can be applied only to the treatment group. The resulting sample defines the final region of common support.

3.2 Installation

To install `comsup`, type: `net install comsup, replace`
from(<https://codeberg.org/fbittmann/comsup/raw/branch/main/>).

3.3 Syntax

```
comsup devar varlist [if] [in] , generate(varname) [options]
```

3.4 Options

- **generate**(*newvar*) specifies the name of the newly created indicator variable that stores the region of common support.
- **tmodel**(*string*) specifies the model for the treatment variable, which must be binary (coded 0/1). The model can be either linear, logit, or probit. The default option is logit. Linear is usually the fastest model.
- **outcome**(*varname*) allows the specification of the outcome variable for the intend analysis. If specified, a second lasso model is estimated where all independent variables (and their interactions and higher order terms) are tested against the outcome. Finally, only variables or terms are included in the propensity score that are related to both the outcome and the treatment. While this can take longer to compute, it ensures that only variables are included in the PS that actually require balancing and common support selection.
- **omodel**(*string*) specifies the model for the outcome variable. The model can be either linear, logit, probit, or poisson.
- **prune**(*string*) prunes the propensity score. The input string must follow this format: "25:5", which means that the resulting propensity score (after a first selection on the standard region of common support) will be divided in 25 equally spaced groups (which does not mean that groups necessarily contain the same number of observations!). Within each group the smaller value of either the treatment or control group must have at least 5 observations. Using this option hence prunes regions in the common support where it might be difficult to find enough matches. This is the only option that allows users to discard sections of the propensity score that are not located at the fringes (if there are "holes" in the propensity score, which can be assess using the graph option).
- **trim**(*#*) trims the fringes of the propensity score. Specified is the percentile that will be trimmed at both ends of the propensity score. For example, if trim(1) is specified, percentile 1 and 99 will be discarded of the propensity score. If both prune() and trim() are specified, the propensity score is first pruned, then trimmed.
- **treatonly** applies the trimming of the propensity score only to treated observations (coded 1).
- **graph** displays a graph that shows the common support before and after selecting the region of common support for a convenient graphical inspection.

- **elasticnet** uses `elasticnet` instead of `lasso` to build the variable selection model(s).
- **folds(#)** is the number of folds for the lasso cross validation procedure (CV). The higher the number of folds, the more stable and precise the findings. While larger values are better, this increases computational time. For details see the helpfile of `lasso`.
- **rseed(#)** sets the random-number seed. Because lasso relies on randomness, results may vary even with identical data over multiple calls to `comsup`. Setting a seed ensures reproducibility.
- **lassoopts(string)** is implemented so users can pass arbitrary options to customize the computation of `lasso` / `elasticnet`.
- **details** compares specified variables before and after selecting the region of common support, which can be helpful for determining the external validity of the resulting sample.
- **psgenerate(newvar)** stores the propensity score in a new variable for further use.
- **replace** overwrites variables, if they already exist (affects `generate()` and `psgenerate()`).

4 Examples

In the **first example**, we demonstrate the use of `comsup` with the NLSW88 dataset, which is distributed with Stata. Our goal is to study the effect of union membership on various outcomes. Based on theoretical considerations, we first select a set of potential confounders that may affect both treatment assignment and the outcomes of interest. We then call `comsup` with these variables. Note that binary and categorical variables require the `i.` prefix, whereas continuous variables require no prefix. Users do not need to specify interactions or higher-order terms explicitly, because the command includes these automatically.

We specify that the two most extreme percentiles of the propensity score be trimmed. In addition, we set a seed to ensure reproducibility and request a graph to visualize how the sample changes. The new variable indicating whether an observation falls within the region of common support is named *insample*. This variable must not already exist when calling `comsup` (unless the `replace` option is specified). `comsup` itself produces no substantive output, aside from the graph (Figure 2), but generates the indicator variable. To inspect the results, the `tabulate` command can be used. We find that 97 observations fall outside the RCS and should not be used in subsequent causal analyses. One can proceed either by dropping these observations or (typically the preferable approach) by using an `if` qualifier in the treatment command to restrict estimation to included observations (that is, `if insample == 1`).

```

. sysuse nlsw88, clear
(NLSW, 1988 extract)
. comsup union i.married i.collgrad i.south i.smsa hours ttl_exp ///
> , tmodel(logit) trim(2) graph rseed(1) generate(insample)
. tab insample

```

common sample indicator	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
0	97	5.17	5.17
1	1,780	94.83	100.00
Total	1,877	100.00	

Figure 2: Region of common support before and after restriction. Some observations outside the RCS are removed, resulting in a modest reduction in sample size.

In the **second example**, we demonstrate how `comsup` can facilitate the broader treatment analysis. When the outcome of interest is already known, it can be incorporated into the command so that only variables influencing both treatment assignment and the outcome are selected, often yielding a more parsimonious model specification. We illustrate this using the NHANES2 dataset. The final treatment effect model is estimated using entropy balancing, for which the additional package `kmatch` must be

installed from SSC.² In this example, we approximate the causal effect of overweight (defined as a BMI above 25) on the probability of having suffered a heart attack.

In a first step, we open the dataset and estimate the model using `comsup`. Again, potential confounders are selected on theoretical grounds, and all binary and categorical variables are specified using the `i.` prefix. Because the dataset is large, we apply both pruning and trimming. Pruning divides the propensity score distribution into 25 equally spaced regions and retains only those regions in which both treatment and control groups contain at least five observations. In addition, we trim one percentile from the remaining distribution. We set a seed for reproducibility and specify an outcome model. Because the outcome is binary, the default logit specification is used. We also illustrate that arbitrary options can be passed to the lasso models, here using clustered estimation.

```
. webuse nhanes2, clear
. generate highbmi = bmi > 25 & !missing(bmi)
. comsup highbmi i.sex age houssiz i.region tresult hgb hct iron ///
>     , prune(25:5) trim(1) outcome(heartatk) omodel(logit) rseed(1) ///
>     lassoopts(cluster(strata)) generate(insample)
when both prune() and trim() are specified, the data are trimmed after pruning
. global indepvars `r(selected_both)`
. tab insample
```

common sample indicator	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
0	223	2.15	2.15
1	10,126	97.85	100.00
Total	10,349	100.00	

```
. kmatch eb highbmi "$indepvars" (heartatk) if insample == 1, targets(2)
(fitting ATT balancing weights ... done)
(fitting ATC balancing weights ... done)
Entropy balancing                                Number of obs = 10,126
                                                Balance tolerance = .00001
Treatment   : highbmi = 1
Targets     : 2
Covariates  : age c.age#c.houssiz c.age#c.hct ...
Matching statistics
```

	Matched			Total	Controls			Balance loss
	Yes	No	Total		Used	Unused	Total	
Treated	4914	0	4914	5212	0	5212	7.64e-17	
Untreated	5212	0	5212	4914	0	4914	1.25e-15	
Combined	10126	0	10126	10126	0	10126		

```
Treatment-effects estimation
```

heartatk	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
ATE	.0019375	.0042816	0.45	0.651	-.0064554 .0103303

2. <https://github.com/benjann/kmatch>

Immediately after estimating `comsup`, we instruct Stata to store the selected confounders (those affecting both treatment assignment and the outcome) in a global macro, which is then used in the outcome model. We specify that both means and standard deviations must be balanced and restrict estimation to observations within the RCS. Finally, we estimate the entropy balancing model. In this example, the ATE is not statistically significant. However, this example is intended only as a simple demonstration of the approach. As a general note, runtime may be substantial depending on the number of observations and covariates specified, owing to the computational demands of the lasso procedures. To reduce computation time, users may specify linear models, which are typically much faster than logit or probit models. In addition, the number of lasso folds can be reduced, trading some stability for faster estimation.

5 Simulation study

In the following section, we demonstrate both the benefits and potential pitfalls of using `comsup`. For this purpose, we set up a simulation study that generates a generic treatment effect scenario.

5.1 Specification

Each Monte Carlo replication generates a synthetic observational dataset with sample size $n \sim \mathcal{U}\{500, 3500\}$. By doing so, a wide range of typical sample sizes is covered. In the next step, three confounders are created.

These variables X_1, X_2, X_3 are generated independently as standard normal:

$$X_j \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1), \quad j = 1, 2, 3.$$

For each replication, coefficients governing treatment assignment are randomly drawn:

$$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 2), \quad \gamma \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1), \quad \delta_1, \delta_2 \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1),$$

and the latent treatment index is defined as

$$L_i = \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \gamma X_{1i} X_{2i} + \delta_1 X_{1i}^2 + \delta_2 X_{2i}^2.$$

Here, the first three terms are the main effects of the confounders, γ controls an interaction term between X_1 and X_2 and the delta terms control higher order influences to make the treatment assignment more complex and realistic. Again, as the respective effect sizes are randomly assigned, a large variety of specifications is created.

Treatment assignment follows a nonlinear selection mechanism through the propensity score

$$p_i = \Lambda(L_i),$$

where $\Lambda(\cdot)$ is the logistic cumulative density function. An imbalance parameter

$$\kappa \sim \mathcal{U}(-0.3, 0.3)$$

introduces random variation in overlap and treatment prevalence. This is especially important when heterogeneous treatment effects are specified, as these are the most biasing when treatment and control group have strongly unequal sizes (Słoczyński 2022). Treatment is assigned as

$$D_i = 1\{U_i + \kappa < p_i\}, \quad U_i \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1).$$

with 1 being the indicator function. The constant treatment effect is drawn each replication as

$$\tau \sim \mathcal{U}(0.1, 1).$$

meaning that there is at least a small treatment effect present in all simulation results. Outcome-model coefficients are drawn independently as

$$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3 \sim \mathcal{U}(0.1, 1),$$

and the error standard deviation varies by replication:

$$\sigma \sim \mathcal{U}(0.5, 4).$$

Outcomes are generated from

$$Y_i = \tau D_i + \alpha_1 X_{1i} + \alpha_2 X_{2i} + \alpha_3 X_{1i} X_{2i} + \varepsilon_i, \quad \varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2).$$

This design induces nonlinear confounding through the treatment assignment process while maintaining a homogeneous average treatment effect, allowing performance comparisons across varying sample sizes, overlap conditions, and noise levels. Note also that the outcome model does not include all variables, interactions, and higher-order terms contained in the treatment assignment model, reflecting the fact that, in practice, outcome generation need not depend on all determinants of treatment assignment. This setup defines the baseline simulation specification.

Heterogeneous treatment effects are not included in this version. In a second simulation specification, the setup is modified slightly to introduce such heterogeneity. Specifically, by adding an interaction term between a confounder and treatment status in the outcome model, treatment effect heterogeneity is induced. The specification is as follows:

$$Y_i = \tau D_i + \alpha_1 X_{1i} + \alpha_2 X_{2i} + \alpha_3 X_{1i} X_{2i} + \alpha_H X_{1i} D_i + \varepsilon_i, \quad \alpha_H \sim \mathcal{U}(0.5, 2).$$

To generate a large number of distinct data-generating scenarios, we conduct 30,000 simulations per specification (homogeneous and heterogeneous). For each generated dataset, we estimate various models to recover the treatment effect, where the target estimand is always τ . We evaluate both the estimated ATE and its standard error to assess bias and variance.

In total, seven Stata estimators are examined. First, we consider three official Stata estimators from the `teffects` suite: `psmatch`, `nnmatch`, and `ra`. For both `psmatch` and `nnmatch`, two nearest neighbors are specified. In addition, `kmatch` provides several treatment effect estimators, of which we consider `kmatch ps` (kernel propensity score matching), `kmatch eb` (entropy balancing), and `kmatch ipw`. For entropy balancing, means and standard deviations are balanced. Finally, we include the community-contributed command `teffects2 ipw` (Słoczyński et al. 2025).

For all estimators, only X_1 and X_2 are included as explanatory variables, with no interactions or higher-order terms. Consequently, all models are misspecified, at least to some degree, reflecting the common empirical practice of omitting nonlinear and interaction terms when specifying treatment models.³

To assess the effect of `comsup`, all estimators are computed twice. First, each estimator is run in its standard specification, some of which already impose some form of common support restriction.⁴ In a second step, `comsup` is applied to the dataset, and all estimators are recomputed using only observations selected within the refined region of common support. For this exercise, we use a relatively simple `comsup` specification and apply only trimming (two percentiles from both tails, applied only to the treated group).⁵

This procedure yields four quantities per estimator in each simulation: the original coefficient estimate and its standard error, and the coefficient estimate and standard error obtained after restricting the sample using `comsup`. Comparing these quantities allows the effect of `comsup` to be quantified precisely. Because the estimators are applied to the same simulated datasets, the *ceteris paribus* condition holds exactly.

5.2 Results

After completing the simulations we evaluate the absolute difference between the target estimand and the factually produced value. To amend the influence of potentially existing extreme outliers, we remove the largest percentile with respect to the differences from the sample (the entire simulation return is removed, that is, for all commands, even if only one command produced the outlier with a given dataset). Since the distribution of the differences is highly skewed (since 0 is the smallest possible value), we evaluate the results using poisson models (exponential mean models), which also allows a clear interpretation.⁶ The only explanatory variable is the binary indicator of whether the RCS restriction based on `comsup` has been applied or not. We start with the model where heterogeneous treatment effects are not explicitly included. For a convenient interpretation, we report results graphically as exponentiated coefficients, meaning that the results can be interpreted as percent changes (Figure 3).

3. For example, one model is specified as follows: `teffects nnmatch (outcome x1 x2) (treat), nn(2) bias(x1 x2)`

4. For `kmatch` estimators `ps` and `ipw`, the `comsup` option is specified.

5. The exact specification is `comsup treat x1 x2, gen(insample) trim(2) treatonly`.

6. <https://blog.stata.com/2011/08/22/use-poisson-rather-than-regress-tell-a-friend/>

Figure 3: Simulation results when no heterogeneous treatment effects are present. Values below 1 indicate a reduction in bias/variance due to the usage of the `comsup` command. $N_{min} = 29,627$. 95% confidence intervals included. Bias is the absolute difference between the target and the factual coefficient (ATE); variance is the standard error of the target coefficient.

On the left side of the graph the change in bias is plotted, separately for each treatment estimation command. It is obvious that the use of `comsup` reduces bias for all commands. For some commands, such as `teffects psmatch`, the reduction is great as it almost reaches 30%. Even entropy balancing profits with a reduction of about 8%. On the right side of the graph the change in the standard errors is shown. Again, when `comsup` is applied, the standard errors become smaller, resulting in short confidence intervals and more precise inference. The reduction is up to 20% for `teffects psmatch`. Some approaches, such as entropy balancing or IPW, do not profit. Summarized, the results so far show a large advantage when `comsup` is applied. However, keep in mind that in all these examples, where there is little treatment heterogeneity, as the absolute difference between ATT and ATC amounts to only 0.228, on average. These numbers are computed using the community-contributed command `hettreatreg` (Słoczyński 2022). In the following simulation, heterogeneous treatment effects are specifically introduced. We show the results in Figure 4.

As it turns out, in this setting, bias can actually increase due to the restriction of the common support, as four commands now have values above 1. Some commands,

Figure 4: Simulation results when heterogeneous treatment effects are introduced. Values below 1 indicate a reduction in bias/variance due to the usage of the `comsup` command. $N_{min} = 29,627$. 95% confidence intervals included.

such as `teffects nmatch`, have biases that are 16% larger when `comsup` is applied. While the variance is still lower, this is an alarming result of the simulation. In this setup, the average absolute difference between the ATT and ATC amounts to 0.775. To see in detail how the different commands react to increasing heterogeneity, we have computed the results again with an additional interaction term for the measurement of heterogeneity (absolute difference between the ATT and ATC). Results are shown in Figure 5. The initially positive effect of a stronger RCS selection turns negative for all methods except for IPW as soon as the heterogeneous treatment effects reach a certain point. While the model itself is flexible and allows for quadratic influences, most lines are almost perfectly straight, hinting at rather linear effects.

6 Discussion

A proper handling of the region of common support is a crucial step in valid treatment effect estimation. While many modern methods, such as propensity score matching and inverse-probability weighting, depend directly on the propensity score and the region of common support, this aspect is often underemphasized in introductory treatments of causal inference. In this contribution, we have highlighted why the region of common

Figure 5: Change in bias by strength of heterogeneous treatment effects. Marginal predicted values, exponentiated. 95% confidence intervals included. The range of the x-axis covers percentile 5 to 95 of the absolute difference between ATT and ATC. $N_{total} = 414,526$.

support is central for identification and estimation. We have also introduced a new Stata command that provides a convenient way to inspect and restrict the region of common support. In addition, our simulation study demonstrates that appropriate handling of the region of common support can improve estimation performance by a non-negligible margin.

We conclude by highlighting several aspects of particular importance. First, the standard way in which many Stata commands handle the region of common support could be improved. This applies both to built-in commands in the `teffects` suite and to several community-contributed commands, some of which require manual specification to enforce common support restrictions. Beyond automatic trimming procedures, more sophisticated treatment model specifications can further improve estimation performance. Given modern computational resources, data-driven approaches such as LASSO can be effectively employed. These methods allow researchers to select relevant terms while reducing the risk of overfitting.

One of the most important findings of our study concerns the interaction between heterogeneous treatment effects and the handling of the region of common support. Both

theoretical considerations and simulation results suggest that the presence of treatment effect heterogeneity can amplify the consequences of strict common support restrictions. As Figure 5 illustrates, when treatment effects are strongly heterogeneous, stricter common support restrictions lead to worse performance across most methods, with the exception of `kmatch ipw`. In contrast to matching-based approaches, IPW assigns weights based on the propensity score. In this context, trimming extreme weights may help stabilize estimates rather than distort them. However, this stabilizing effect does not appear to hold for `teffects2 ipw`, which implements a similar weighting strategy. One possible explanation is that its doubly robust structure may increase sensitivity to model misspecification, although the exact mechanism remains unclear. Overall, researchers should exercise caution when substantial treatment effect heterogeneity is expected.

This creates a practical dilemma in applied research, where the data-generating process is typically unknown. When treatment effects are approximately homogeneous, stricter common support restrictions may improve estimation. However, when heterogeneity is substantial, the same restrictions may increase bias by systematically excluding relevant subpopulations. Although we cannot provide a definitive rule, we offer several practical recommendations. First, if strong treatment effect heterogeneity is suspected based on theory or prior evidence, careful inspection of the region of common support is advisable. After restricting the sample, researchers should compare covariate distributions between treatment and control groups. If the resulting sample appears highly selective or substantially different from the full population, strict common support restrictions may be inappropriate. In such cases, alternative estimation strategies beyond propensity score matching or inverse-probability weighting may be required.

Furthermore, researchers can empirically assess the presence of treatment effect heterogeneity using Stata's `teffects` framework (for example via the `ATET` option to inspect the `ATT`) or community-contributed commands such as `hettreatreg`. Finally, it is important to note that not all methods evaluated here are equally effective in recovering causal effects, as shown in a recent comparative study (Bittmann 2026). Some estimators fail to recover specified effects even in favorable settings. An exception is entropy balancing, which performs well across most specifications. As the simulation results indicate, entropy balancing still benefits from a more restrictive region of common support, provided that treatment effect heterogeneity is not too pronounced.

7 References

- Bittmann, F. 2026. Matching, weighting, or regression? Evidence from a comprehensive simulation study of Stata treatment effect estimators. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18267321>.
- Caliendo, M., and S. Kopeinig. 2008. Some practical guidance for the implementation of propensity score matching. *Journal of economic surveys* 22(1): 31–72.
- Huber, M., M. Lechner, and C. Wunsch. 2013. The performance of estimators based on the propensity score. *Journal of Econometrics* 175(1): 1–21.
- Lechner, M. 2008. A note on the common support problem in applied evaluation studies. *Annales d'Économie et de Statistique* 217–235.
- Lechner, M., and A. Strittmatter. 2019. Practical procedures to deal with common support problems in matching estimation. *Econometric Reviews* 38(2): 193–207.
- Li, M. 2013. Using the propensity score method to estimate causal effects: A review and practical guide. *Organizational Research Methods* 16(2): 188–226.
- Pearl, J. 2009. *Causality*. Cambridge University Press.
- Ranstam, J., and J. A. Cook. 2018. LASSO regression. *Journal of British Surgery* 105(10): 1348–1348.
- Rosenbaum, P. R., and D. B. Rubin. 1983. The central role of the propensity score in observational studies for causal effects. *Biometrika* 70(1): 41–55.
- Słoczyński, T. 2022. Interpreting OLS estimands when treatment effects are heterogeneous: Smaller groups get larger weights. *Review of Economics and Statistics* 104(3): 501–509.
- Słoczyński, T., S. D. Uysal, and J. M. Wooldridge. 2025. Covariate Balancing and the Equivalence of Weighting and Doubly Robust Estimators of Average Treatment Effects. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.18563>.

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